

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

As the world becomes ever more connected, the appeal of learning a new language is clear. Whether for business or pleasure, being able to communicate on an international level can bring many benefits. Nowadays most students of higher education want to use effective study methods so they can learn a language fast and speak it.

INTRODUCTION

The modernization of higher professional education dictates the search for new methods, techniques and technologies that would contribute to the effective teaching of students, including foreign languages. Modern education in order to achieve high educational results should be characterized by constant information content of the content of education, activation of the pace of learning with the involvement of modern information technologies. In modern scientific and methodological literature, more and more attention is paid by the authors to the justification of the high educational potential and the effectiveness of the use of innovative teaching technologies in the system of teaching English in higher education.

Currently, the state educational standard has high requirements for students. Short terms of mastering topics, a large amount of information are modern conditions for the general educational process. In order to fulfill such requests, new teaching methods must be found. Due to this, in the methodology of teaching English, there has been a transition from a communicative approach to an interactive one. The interactive approach is one of the varieties of the communicative approach.

MAIN PART

At the present stage of development of higher professional education, there is a tendency to reduce the number of classroom hours and increase the hours allocated for independent work of students. In this regard, we can state the fact that today the role of the teacher in the educational process is being transformed. Until recently, the teacher was perceived as the main source of information, but today his role can be more fully characterized as the organizer and leader, expert and consultant of the educational and self-educational activities of future specialists¹.

¹ Gladilina, I.P. Some methods of work at English lessons / I.P. Gladilina // Foreign languages at school. - 2013. - No. 3.

Such transformations became possible due to the emergence and widespread introduction of innovative and more effective technologies, forms and means of education into the educational process of higher education, which make it possible to optimize the process of professional training of future specialists as part of their studies at the university.

The high productivity and efficiency of innovative technologies in the context of training future specialists is justified by their multifunctionality. Thus, innovative pedagogical technologies perform the following functions in the educational process: informative; formative; motivating; systematizing; controlling.

Innovative technologies and teaching methods make it possible to achieve the following goals: accessibility of the perception of educational material; systematization of knowledge; development of creative abilities of students; self-education; removing the psychological barrier (fear of communicating, making a mistake); comprehension of educational material, analysis of learned material.

The purpose of interactive learning is that all participants in the lesson are in interaction. They are all actively involved in the learning process. The teacher acts as an assistant.

In the course of interactive communication, students learn to think, solve problems, make decisions and participate in discussions. Modern pedagogy has many interactive methods.

Among them are the following:

- Creative tasks;
- Educational games (role-playing games, educational games, etc.);
- Work in small groups, pairs, triplets (reception "2.4, together");
- "Carousel" method;
- "Aquarium";
- "Brainstorming" or another name "brainstorming";
- "Openwork saw";
- "Brownian motion";
- Drawing up a mental map;
- "Choose a position";
- Debates;
- Use of project methodology.

This list can be replenished, because each teacher can implement their own techniques and methods.

The scope of one article does not make it possible to describe all the interactive methods of teaching English, so we will consider only those that are used in practice.

CONCLUSION

To conclude teaching a language can help in both your personal and professional life. It can boost other skills and improve your cultural understanding. Each student has unique talent, interest in learning a new language. So, a professional teacher should find the most suitable effective methods of teaching a foreign language according to student's own desire, capability and time.

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